

Zeno is a PhD student working in the interdisciplinary intersection between Artificial Intelligence and Language and therefore has two supervisors, each expert in their field. He is halfway through his PhD and is disappointed by the limited attention his initially promising work received. Now in his third year, he is busy with some computational linguistical experiments, and to his surprise, his results are even more impressive than he had hoped. In his next meeting with his supervisors, he discusses his findings and his supervisors are equally enthusiastic.

However, after a discussion with a fellow PhD student a week later, he uncovers a significant error in his experimental setup, an issue that only arises from the complexities of his interdisciplinary approach. If he were to publish his results he would not be lying anywhere, and the mistake would be visible just as much in the paper as in the code. Despite this, Zeno realizes that the specific nature of his research might prevent the wider linguistic community from spotting this mistake. He faces a dilemma: he could potentially move forward with publication, as the error might go unnoticed by many.

Since Zeno has already convinced his supervisors, he realizes the language research community where he plans to publish will likely not see through this error either. He reflects that although some researchers might spot his mistake, the research community does not work with negative citations, and even when later work marks a paper as faulty, this will take a lot of time to be caught up by the community if it ever is.

Questions:

- 1) What implementations could the research community as a whole take to increase accountability for mistakes such as Zeno's?
- 2) Do you think a situation such as the one Zeno is in is uncommon in the academic world?